

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	1.9	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	38
B05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	2.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	42
B06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	1.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	36
C05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	92	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	1840
E06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	52.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	1056
F05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	101	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	2020
F06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	41.5	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	830
G05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	0.74	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	14.8
G06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	39.6	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	792
H05	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
H06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	33.2	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	664
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	4.9	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	98
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	OK	3.3	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	66
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
F07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fl	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				0	16134						16134
		2.8	1.3	25	15280						15305
		3	1.4	27	15144						15171
		2.6	1.2	24	15760						15784
				0	14513						14513
				0	15663						15663
				0	16265						16265
				0	16157						16157
		97	87	1195	14740						15935
		56.7	48.9	699	15231						15930
		107	96	1199	13336						14535
		44.9	38	561	15636						16197
		1.3	0.37	10	15959						15969
		42.8	36.3	567	16578						17145
				0	16383						16383
		36.2	30.2	472	16472						16944
				0	15920						15920
				0	15820						15820
		6.2	3.8	66	15893						15959
		4.4	2.5	46	16233						16279
				0	15942						15942
				28	16475						16503

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	0	0	4342.7
	1	1	4882	5288.8	4366.4
	1	1	343	475.74	231.17
	1	1	4810	5786.5	4321.4
	1	1	0	0	4975
	1	1	0	0	4363.1
	1	1	0	0	4872.4
	1	1	0	0	4268.3
	1	1	5725	7984	4691.8
	1	1	5200	7744.6	4234.3
	1	1	5685	7823.9	4664.2
	1	1	5029	7248.5	4057.4
	1	1	5139	6738.2	4456
	1	1	5249	8370.2	4118.7
	1	1	0	0	4369.9
	1	1	5098	8163.8	4014.5
	1	1	0	0	3916.8
	1	1	0	0	3878.5
	1	1	4405	6444.7	3806
	1	1	4352	6763.8	3753.2
	1	1	0	0	3613.5
	1	1	4117	4942.8	3682

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68	TotalCNVMax68
4342.7							
4367.9					2.33	1.56	
231.61					2.52	1.72	
4323.7					2.18	1.45	
4975							
4363.1							
4872.4							
4268.3							
4938.7					94.4	89.1	
4388.3					54.8	50.8	
4924.9					104.2	98.4	
4168					43.2	39.7	
4457.4					1	0.53	
4259.3					41.2	37.9	
4369.9							
4130.1					34.8	31.7	
3916.8							
3878.5							
3816.9					5.5	4.3	
3761.7					3.84	2.86	
3613.5							
3684.1							

